

Value Investing: An Empirical Study of IT and FMCG Sector in India

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Abstract: Invented in the early 90s, value investing is the process of identifying and investing into the stocks based on their historical financial ratios. Value investing has gained attention from the investors to outperform the market. Over a period of time, various measures are proposed to classify the stock as value stock. This paper used price-to-earning and price-to-book-value as the value measures and tested the suitability of value investing in the Indian capital market. Ten years data of IT and FMCG sectors are analysed. The findings suggest that the value investing is more acceptable in the IT sector than the FMCG sector.

Keywords: Value Investing, Value Stock, Growth Stock, Value Premium

1. Introduction

The success of investing in stocks is measured with the portfolio returns. Over a period of time many strategies are developed to spot the undervalued and probable outperforming stocks to increase the portfolio returns. One of the strategy is value investing which aims to identify the undervalued stocks. The roots of value investing can be traced back in the year 1920s when Benjamin Graham and David Dodd worked together at Columbia Business School. He and Dodd proposed a methodology to identify stocks trading at a price less than their true value and stressed that the rational investor can take advantage of overly optimistic or pessimistic valuations of the stock to outperform the market.

The stock trading at a price lower than it's worth is considered as value stock. The value stock has a potential to offer superior returns to the investor. On the contrary, the stocks which are trading at fair price but possess ability to outperform the market due to their potential are termed as growth stock. Based on financial parameter, value stock carries lower values of measuring variables like price-to-earning (P/E), price-to-book (P/B), and cash flow-to-price (CF/P). The stocks carrying high values for these variables are termed as growth stocks.

The value portfolio can be created with two options. First, the qualitative approach where the management of the firm, product portfolio, future potential of the sector and firm, technological advancement, economic environment are important to arrive at investment decision. The other option is quantitative approach where the set of financial ratios calculated from the financial statements of the firm decide the investment decision.

The topic of value investing is well researched topic but has not yet reached to conclusive stage. The present research is proposed due the fact that mixed response from the various empirical evidences across the countries. Firstly, the purpose of this paper is to underline the earlier findings in the area of value investing. Second objective is to verify the presence or absence of value indicators in Indian market. And if present, which indicators are the strongest? The study considers the stocks from information technology (IT) and fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) sector only.

2. Literature Review

Basu (1977) is one of the early cohorts of the value investing. Their study was to analyse the NYSE traded stock and their price-earning (P/E) multiple. The fourteen years data was analysed in 5 equally weighted portfolios. The study found that the low P/E ratio (value stock) portfolio deliver 6 per cent more yields that high P/E ratio (growth stock) portfolio. Rosenberg et al. (1985) evaluated the stock performance based on book to market (B/M) approach with portfolio of 1,400 securities. Their hedge portfolio of high B/M value stock and short B/M value stock had an average monthly return of 0.36 per cent during the 12 years period of study. They observe the robust seasonality of the stock performance where mean January return is ~ 1.7 per cent and thereafter following the down ward trend.

Chan et al. (1991) studied the relationship between mean returns of Japanese stocks. The portfolios were constructed using book to market ratio, earning to price ratio and cash flow to price ratio. The yearly rebalancing of four equally weighted portfolio showed that firms with high and low book to market ration fetched a return of 2.43 per cent 1.33 per cent per month respectively. The other measures cash to price and earning to price were also positively correlated with high book to market ratio showing similar portfolio performance. Fama and French (1992) undertook the comparative analysis of mean portfolio returns and market returns of 100 equally weighted portfolios based on company size, market capitalization and book to market ratio. The study documents the existence of B/M effect controlling the size and vice-versa. The market returns was showing increasing trend as B/M increases and the effect was stronger for the smaller stocks.

Lakonishok et al. (1994) in their work introduced growth to sales as value measure in addition to well researched several measures like book to market (B/M), cash flow to price (CF/P) and earning to price (E/P). The study is based on equally weighted portfolios from five years of accounting data. The data analysis revealed that first decile portfolio formed on growth to sales ratio outperformed tenth-decile portfolio with difference of 6.8 per cent. The highest difference of 11 per cent per year over five years was found in the portfolio based on cash flow to price ratio. The concept was further extended between large stock and small stock. The similar results were obtained indicating presence of value premium in large as well as small stocks.

Arshanapalli et al. (1998) documented the outperformance of value stock over growth stock in sample countries during January 1975 to December 1995. The outperformance was both, in terms of absolute returns and risk adjusted returns. The study confirms the lower spread between growth and value measures at international levels.

Davis, J. et al. (2000) conducted a study on firms listed on NYSE post 1964. The study was based on six value weighted portfolios formed with small and large stocks bifurcated with low, high and medium book to market ratio. The findings of the study confirmed that value portfolio based on book to market ratio earns 0.48 per cent more than growth portfolio. The study was in line with earlier findings to conclude that value premium exists and on higher side in small stocks as compared to large stocks. Bartov and Kim (2004) in their study based on equal weighted portfolio of sample spreading over 1980 to 1998 highlighted the use of accruals in stock valuation. They used both, accruals and B/M quintiles to analysed the buy and hold return from the portfolio. Their findings suggested that the higher B/M quintile portfolio surpasses the lowest quintile by 14.1% and the low accrual quintile portfolio beats the high accrual quintile by 7.5%. The findings are enhancement to the observations of La Porta et al. (1997).

Chan et al. (2000) researched the rational asset pricing hypothesis, new paradigm viewpoint and behavioral or institutional explanation in the study. The six U.S equity asset classes bifurcated by size and style (value or growth) support the behavioral explanation for the stock-price performance. Griffin and Lemmon (2002) added new measure, O-scores to analyse the portfolio performance. O-score is the representations of firm's various financial ratios and other accounting information. The firm having high scores is considered as distressed firm with high probability of bankruptcy. The findings of the study showed that the portfolios based on higher B/M ratios outperformed portfolio based on low B/M. The study also demonstrated that significant part of the return range occurs around earnings. The return range for the high O-score group, small (big) firms with high B/M minus low is 3.39 per cent (2.14 per cent) using the aggregate return the day before earnings to the day after.

Chan and Lakonishok(2004) came out with the new results on an updated and expanded sample. They conclude that the value investing generates excess return over growth stock due to behavioral considerations and agency costs as the root cause of value-growth differential. Mohanram (2005) combines the traditional fundamentals with tailored made measures to create an index-GSCORE. He observed GSCORE based long (buy)-short (sell) strategy generates extra return. However, the study contradicts with earlier results to confirm the behavioral aspects of the investing.

Hyde (2014) conducted a study on countries forming part of MSCI index which covers 21 countries. The study, based on Piotroski's F-score revealed that higher returns are

associated with the value of F-score and vice-versa. He found that, except Brazil, the value premium is present in all the countries due to behavioral biases of the portfolio construction. In the recent studies by Palazzo et al. (2018) endorsed the presence of value premium for the sample studied during the time period starting from 2005 to 2015. The study was conducted at Brazilian stock exchange and the findings were in support of the value investing strategy to obtain higher returns as documented by the earlier findings of Testa (2011) and Kargin (2002).

3. Methodology

The longitudinal research design is followed in the present work with deductive approach as the theory is already in existence. Following to the Bell and Bryman(2018) the quantitative data is collected from the reliable sources and tested using statistical methods to validate the theory during the period of research. The research work is free from the any subjectivity as the statistical analysis is based on objective data.

Due to the personal interest of the author, two sectors, Information Technology (IT) and Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) are selected for the research. The filter of data availability is applied to include the company as sample. Total 128 companies from IT and 85 companies from FMCG sector find place in the final sample size.

Indian economy sustained the financial crisis of 2008 and moved ahead in the following years. Considering the performance of stock market from 2011 till recent time, the researcher has decided to consider the 10 years data from January 2011 to December 2020. This will make the present work as one of the recent work in the area of value investing and 10 years' time period is meaningful to contribute on the idea of value investing and to update and enhance the understanding about the topic.

3.1. Data

The research is based on secondary data. Based on literature research variables such as price-to-earning, price-to-book are identified for the purpose of study. The historical values about the research variables for the sample firms are obtained from Prowess data base maintained by Center of Monitoring Indian Economy. The NIFTY index is used as proxy for the market return. The monthly returns of market value is obtained from Prowess. For risk free return, T-bill returns are considered and the values for the period of research are obtained from traningeconomics.com.

3.2. Data Analysis

The research is carried out with objective to verify the presence of value premium in the IT and FMCG sectors of the Indian capital market. Using the deductive approach, the hypotheses are tested on the data collected from the secondary sources. In the first step,

the data compiled and arranged in ascending order based on P/E ratio and P/B ratios. Then the data is bifurcated into three categories namely value (first quartile), growth (fourth quartile) and neutral (second and third quartile) based on P/E and P/B ratio values. Following the Basu (1977), Chan et al. (1991), Fama and French (1992) and Lakonishok et al. (1994) equal weighted portfolios consisting of value stock and growth stock are created. Total 120 (12 monthly portfolio X 10 years) value portfolios are created for each sector. Likewise 120 growth portfolios are created for each sector. Thus, total 240 value portfolio (120 x 2 sectors) and equal number of growth portfolios are created. The portfolio rebalancing is conducted at the end of every month to compare their performances. The Neutral stocks are excluded from the study. Following Bodie et al. (2011) the portfolios returns are risk adjusted using Sharpe and Treynor ratio. The risk adjusted positive return indicate portfolios outperform the market negative returns proposed risk free investments are safer investment option than stock portfolio. The statistical significance of the results is tested by developing following null (H_0) and alternate (H_1) hypothesis.

H_0 = the returns from value portfolio are not higher than the returns of growth portfolio during 2011 to 2020.

H_1 = the returns from value portfolio are higher than the returns of growth portfolio during 2011 to 2020.

Based on the value of skewness and kurtosis, it is confirmed that data follows non-normal distribution and therefore Mann-Whitney U test is applied to test the hypothesis.

4. Empirical Findings

4.1. Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics about the monthly portfolios of the two sectors is given in Table 1. The monthly portfolio return is the product of stock return and its weightage in the portfolio. For the research period ten years from 2011 to 2020, the value portfolios based on IT stocks shows monthly positive return for 64 months out of 120 months and the value portfolio based on FMCG stocks shows a monthly positive return for 56 months for the same period. The growth portfolios based on IT stocks shows monthly positive return for 59 months out of 120 months and the growth portfolio based on FMCG stocks shows a monthly positive return for 58 months during the period of research. Comparing the monthly returns, the frequency of positive returns is more in the value portfolio of IT stocks than value portfolio of FMCG stocks.

Table 1: Monthly Portfolio Returns

Year	Value Portfolio				Growth Portfolio			
	IT Stocks		FMCG Stocks		IT Stocks		FMCG Stocks	
	Positive Returns	Negative Returns						
2011	6	6	5	7	7	5	6	6
2012	8	4	7	5	7	5	6	6
2013	9	3	6	6	7	5	5	7
2014	7	5	5	7	8	4	6	6
2015	8	4	6	6	9	3	6	6
2016	6	6	6	6	7	5	4	8
2017	4	8	5	7	6	6	8	4
2018	7	5	7	5	7	5	7	5
2019	4	8	5	7	5	7	6	6
2020	5	7	4	8	6	6	4	8
Total	64	56	56	64	59	51	58	62

4.2. Value Premium

Referring to the Fama and French (1992) the positive difference between the returns of value portfolios and growth portfolios is termed as value premium. The statistical information about the month wise value premium of researched data is given theTable 2.The numbers reported are the frequency of positive return earned by the value portfolio over the growth stock of the both the sectors i.e IT and FMCG. The IT sectors has produced more number of times value premium than the FMCG stock during the same period. However, the comparison of frequency of returns and quantum of returns, portfolios based on FMCG stock has produced higher returns than the IT sector portfolios. The -in the table represents growth portfolio outperformed the value portfolio indicating the absence of value premium.

Table 2: Value Premium

	Year	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Total
IT	Number	5	3	--	5	7	--	--	6	8	7	41
FMCG	of months	--	--	5	4	--	6	--	4	--	4	23

Source: Authors calculation

4.3. Risk adjusted returns

As the stock market is risk based investment, the risk adjusted return justify the fair compensation to the investor. In the present work, the risk adjusted returns are calculated

for both, value and growth portfolios using Shareperatio and Treynor ratios as proposed in Sharpe (1994) and Cheah (2012). The Sharpe and Treynor ratios are based on annual portfolio returns. Positive values of the ratio confirm the portfolios outperformance over the market index and between two portfolios, higher values indicates more returns per unit of risk. In the researched data the risk adjusted returns of IT and FMCG stocks based on Sharpe and Treynor ratio are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Risk Adjusted Returns

Year	Sharpe Ratio				Treynor Ratio			
	IT Stocks		FMCG Stocks		IT Stocks		FMCG Stocks	
	Value Portfolio	Growth Portfolio						
2011	+1.30	-	+0.22	-	+1.01	-	+0.05	-
2012	+0.60	-	-	-	+0.012	-	-	-
2013	-	+0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-
2014	-	-	+0.16	-	-	-	-	-
2015	+1.15	+0.66	-	+0.02	--	-	+0.09	-
2016	+2.67	+0.11	+3.10	+0.06	+1.16	+1.11	+1.11	+0.06
2017	+2.15	-	-	-	+1.89	+2.00	+1.20	-
2018	+1.90	0.32	+1.85	-	-	-	-	-
2019	-	+0.87	-	+0.01	-	-	-	+0.08
2020	+3.11	-	+1.46	+0.15	+2.11	-	-	-
Total	7*	5*	5*	4*	5*	2*	4*	2*

Source: Authors calculation. Only positive returns are reported in term of per cent. *no of times positive returns generated during period of research. - indicates negative returns.

4.4. Hypothesis Testing

The hypothesis as mentioned in the research methodology is tested to generalize the findings of the study. The normality of the data is tested using Skewness and Kurtosis. The values of skewness and Kurtosis for IT sectors is 2.1 and 6.21. The values of Skewness and Kurtosis for FMCG sectors data is 1.5 and 4.20. The values are not following the requirements of normal distribution. Therefore the non-parametric test like Mann-Whitney U test using SPSS 26 is applied to test the hypothesis. The SPSS output of the IT sector and FMCG sector is given in Table 4 and 5 respectively.

Table 4: p value and hypothesis testing of IT sector stock portfolio

Year	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Mann-Whitney U	77	76	77	74	81	82	81	78	77	82
Wilconxon W	165	167	165	158	175	177	175	169	165	168
p-value (2 tailed)	0.048	0.455	0.012	0.648	0.077	0.076	0.029	0.536	0.088	0.098

Table 5: p value and hypothesis testing of FMCG sector stock portfolio

Year	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	20120
Mann-Whitney U	88	85	85	80	78	82	95	91	89	90
Wilconxon W	167	166	166	162	160	163	175	172	170	171
p-value (2 tailed)	0.715	0.852	0.026	0.444	0.652	0.036	0.069	0.011	0.061	0.548

The significance of results is interpreted from the p-values. The difference between the two portfolio returns of IT stocks is statistically significant at 0.5 and .1 level of significance for 3 and 4 times respectively. The difference between the two portfolio returns of FMCG stocks is statistically significant at 0.5 and .1 level of significance for 3 and 2 times respectively.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

As proposed by Fama and French (1970) it is difficult for the stock investments to beat the market return due to efficient market hypothesis (EMH) and this fact is observed for the sample studied in this paper. The market return is higher than the annual returns of the value and growth portfolios from both IT and FMCG sector. The findings are not unidirectional to advocate one particular investment strategy. The outcomes are in line with the objectives set to apply the theories of value investing sector-wise in Indian capital market. Each sector in the Indian economy has its own sector-specific characteristic. Due to the listing of diversified companies on the stock exchanges, it is necessary to test the suitability of theory sector-wise rather in a generalized way. The findings for IT sector are in line with earlier empirical evidences like Basu (1977), Lakonishok et al. (1994), Palazzo et al. (2018) and Bartov and Kim (2004). However, the FMCG sector has given mixed results. The frequency of positive return from the value portfolio of IT stock is more than the value portfolios of FMCG stocks, indicating value investing is more suitable for investor of IT sector in India during period of research. Investing in the stocks is an art. The search for value stock using balance sheet approach is losing its charm now a days. Due to availability of superior and reliable information using professionally managed data base the balance sheet approach is common and known to most of the investor. May be in future, the future earning potential of firm would surpass the historical financial values. To conclude, the true importance of the difference may have been best noted by Benjamin Graham. In the short run, the market is a voting machine, but in the long run, it is a weighing machine” (Arnott et al., 2005).

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